

System approach to close the employment gap and create a more inclusive labour market for vulnerable groups.
 (Project number: 101094526)

Monitoring Framework

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CTMO	Context, Theories, Mechanisms, and Outcomes
WP	Work Package
CMO	Context, Mechanisms and Outcomes
SCCT	Social Cognitive Career Theory
TTM	Transtheoretical Model
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
IPS	Individual Placement and Support
CBT	Cognitive Behavioural Therapy

Abstract

This document outlines the implementation of a monitoring framework within the four living labs. The monitoring framework aims to monitor the project goals, i.e. monitoring the support of vulnerable unemployed individuals in accessing employment while fostering organizational mobility of employees. In doing so it uses both the quantitative evaluation of the implementation of an intervention package in the four Living Labs as well as using both quantitative and qualitative measurements to understand the mechanisms of why these intervention packages work or not, for whom and in which context. It thus helps steering the implementation process in the Living Labs (WP2) as well as the process of upscaling this approach, identifying policy indicators and standards of good practice as policy advice at EU-level (WP3).

This systematic approach comprises of several sequential stages. As it is important to successfully implement the intervention package as well as test its' effectiveness, a central aspect to this monitoring framework is the Realist Evaluation. This approach aims to identify mechanisms driving change, and anticipated outcomes for unemployed individuals and employees seeking labour market mobility. Active participation of employers and other relevant stakeholders is essential in identifying effective strategies and the fundamental reasoning behind them. In the subsequent implementation phase, tailored action plans, specific to each living lab aim to support inflow and mobility. The Data Collection phase utilizes a mixed method approach combining both quantitative and qualitative methods, including questionnaires, interviews, and participatory strategies, along with mentoring and coaching processes to empower and gain insights from individuals. This means that only after the identification of the action plans, the main specific monitoring indicators can be identified and interview schedules be made specific. The monitoring framework report thus will be a living document, to be updates at several stages of this process: after the identification of the action plans and during its implementation process in all four Living Labs.

Executive summary

Introduction

The Synclusive project aims to develop and evaluate a comprehensive approach to support vulnerable groups in the labor market across four European Living Labs. These Labs involve two target groups (job seekers and employees) and regional stakeholders like municipalities, employers, educational institutes, and communities. The ENGINE approach guides the design and implementation of preferably evidence-based interventions to be tailored for targeting individuals, organizations, and regions, and also use interventions that are more practice-based. This will require an emphasis in implementation research: the question will be how do we succeed in implementing evidence-based approaches and what are the drivers and barriers of such efforts for each stakeholder and for differing evidence-based approaches during the project.

The interventions range from training job seekers by enhancing their self-efficacy and skills for job searching to supervisors and service providers to fostering inclusive work environments. A monitoring framework is established to monitor and analyse the implementation of interventions, and to understand what works for whom, in what circumstances, and why. It's designed for real-time adjustments and standardized data collection across Labs. This evolving framework focuses on realist evaluation, adapting as contexts and outcomes evolve. This document initiates Synclusive's data collection process, set to evolve alongside the realist evaluation. Work Packages 2 and 4 involve designing, implementing, and monitoring interventions across Living Labs, while WP3 compares Labs, utilizing a multilevel perspective for analysis. The monitoring framework and indicators will steer this process across quantitative and qualitative assessments in these work packages. The monitoring framework report will be a 'living document', which needs updates as the project progresses.

Goals

The monitoring framework presented in this document adopts a mixed-methods approach for data collection, amalgamating quantitative and qualitative data analysis. It centers on three key elements: **the ENGINE outcomes, the Living Labs' specific context, and intervention levels at individual, organizational, and regional scales.**

Two primary project goals emerge: **monitor the interventions implementation across Living Labs and comprehending what, for whom, under what circumstances, and why interventions work or don't work.** Quantitative and qualitative evaluations drive these aims, facilitated by specific indicators and methodologies. The evaluation assesses intervention effectiveness across generic and Living Lab-specific indicators. It incorporates quantitative analyses evaluating intervention effectiveness in the four Labs, considering individual, organizational, and regional factors as potential moderators. The realist evaluation explores mechanisms influencing intervention impact, identifying Lab-specific and overarching mechanisms. For both quantitative and qualitative analyses, indicators need selection based on relevance, reliability, and usability. These indicators aim to measure the impact of intervention packages on vulnerable unemployed inflow and employee mobility, standardized across Living Labs.

Realist Evaluation

The **Realist Evaluation** approach (reference) within the Synclusive project aims to understand what interventions work for specific individuals, organisations, and coalitions, in what conditions, and why. It involves identifying, testing, and refining effective components of interventions. The process consists of **four key steps:**

Program theory: Identifying theories that explain how interventions work.

CMO (Context-Mechanisms-Outcomes) / Hypotheses: Developing hypothetical configurations to explore what might work for whom (considering all the stakeholders), under what circumstances, and why.

Evidence-based: Testing theories through interventions/implementation, and research through data collection and analysis, employing a mixed-methods approach.

Analysis and synthesis: Identifying what worked for whom, under what circumstances, and why.

The application of this approach involves selecting program theories relevant to vulnerable unemployed people, developing hypothetical configurations (CMO), and analyzing potential interventions across different contexts. The focus is on

understanding mechanisms that trigger outcomes and the conditions necessary for success. The theories selected, such as Social Cognitive Career Theory (Bandura, 1997) and Transtheoretical Model of Change (Prochaska & Norcross, 2018), emphasize elements like self-efficacy, stages of change, and career adaptability. These theories form the basis for understanding how interventions might function for vulnerable individuals. The subsequent steps involve delineating specific CMO configurations, which connect context, mechanisms, and outcomes. Examples of potential interventions include skills training, job coaching, and community-based support. Each intervention is mapped to its contextual indicators, mechanisms, and intended outcomes. The context indicators encompass socio-economic conditions, demographics, policy regulations, labor market conditions, and technological access. Mechanisms represent psychological processes like motivation, self-efficacy, trust, and self-esteem that link context and outcomes. Final outcomes encompass mobility and employability; and mid-term outcomes includes, improved job prospects, increased employability, reduced stress, enhanced financial stability, and community development. The mixed-methods approach will gather diverse data sources to understand these complex interactions better, facilitating a comprehensive understanding. The analysis and synthesis phase will involve in-depth analysis and multilevel analysis to identify associations and relationships between contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes. This knowledge aims to enhance intervention strategies and refine them for better effectiveness.

Multilevel Analysis

The multilevel analysis will be applied for evaluating intervention impacts in the Synclusive project involving defining and measuring indicators across individual, organizational, and regional levels in the Living Labs. The framework explores the two main outcomes: Inflow labour market and up/sideward mobility; and mediators as self-efficacy, confidence, and trust, for explaining why the chosen interventions influence employment and mobility outcomes. Moderators like gender, age, and motivation can affect the strength of relationships between variables and inform which participants will especially benefit from the interventions. These factors are vital for precision in research findings and intervention design. The evaluation involves three measurement stages during intervention implementation (i.e., before, in the middle and after the

implementation), aiming to assess impact levels at various intervals. However, specific timelines depend on the nature of interventions and Living Lab action plans. Determining the required number of respondents involves considerations of statistical power analysis and/or other methods of sample size definition for Job seekers and employees per Living Lab. However, the characteristics of the regional labour markets may, for example, affect these numbers. The framework also introduces the multilevel perspective analysis, focusing on understanding how individual characteristics and Living Lab environments interact to influence employment outcomes. Statistical techniques like cluster analysis and multi-level mixed estimation will be employed to analyze relationships between individual and Lab-level variables.

Conclusion

The **Synclusive project** lays the groundwork for a comprehensive and quantitative evaluation of interventions **aimed at supporting vulnerable groups in the labor market across multiple European Living Labs**. By integrating both quantitative and qualitative methodologies, this **monitoring framework** seeks to comprehensively assess the impact of preferably evidence-based and tailored interventions on individuals, organizations, and regional communities. The monitoring framework emphasizes a mixed-methods approach, **focusing on ENGINE outcomes**, Living Lab contexts, and intervention levels across various scales. The framework encompasses indicators spanning individual, organizational, and regional levels, exploring mediators like employability and mobility and considering moderators such as gender, age, and motivation. The planning involves meticulous measurement stages during intervention implementation, aiming to gauge impact levels across intervals. However, adaptation to the evolving nature of interventions and action plans within Living Labs is key. The nuclear methodology used - **Realist Evaluation approach** - operates through four distinct steps: developing program theories, formulating hypothetical configurations, testing these configurations through a mixed-methods approach, and ultimately identifying effective interventions and their underlying mechanisms. The integration of theories like Social Cognitive Career Theory and Transtheoretical Model of Change lay the foundation for understanding how interventions might function for vulnerable individuals. These theories guide the delineation of specific configurations linking context, mechanisms, and outcomes. Various potential interventions –ranging from

individual training to community-based support – are mapped against contextual indicators and mechanisms, aiming to bring about positive outcomes such as increased employability, reduced stress, and community development. The iterative process of data collection, coding, and multilevel analysis will shed light on the relationships between contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes, thereby refining intervention strategies for optimal effectiveness. The collaborative effort across Living Labs underscores the commitment to foster inclusive practices and support the most vulnerable in accessing and thriving within the labor market.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The project Synclusive aims to develop, implement, and evaluate an innovative, integral, interdisciplinary systems' approach to promote the inflow, retention, and further development of vulnerable groups in the labour market. In four Living Labs in different European contexts (Bulgaria, Finland, the Netherlands, Portugal), relevant regional stakeholders will work together for these aims: e.g. the vulnerable target groups themselves, the municipalities, employers, civil societies, (vocational) educational and coaching institutes and communities.

The ENGINE is the primary approach to guide the design and implementation of an integrated package of interventions in each of the four Living Labs. This intervention package is a tailor-made, as far as possible evidence-based integrated package of interventions at individual, organisational and regional levels and directed at different vulnerable groups and stakeholders, attuned to each other. Interventions can, for example, include training of supervisors of organisations to develop the talents of their personnel and create an inclusive work environment, and coaching of job seekers.

A monitoring framework is created 1) to quantitatively assess the impact of the intervention package; 2) to understand a) what works (or doesn't work)?, b) for whom (and to what extent)?, (c) in which circumstances does it work?, and (d) how and why does it work?; and 3) to guide the implementation of the intervention package and to provide real-time indications to adapt this implementation process timely when needed. The overall aim of the monitoring framework is also to attune the overall data collection to be done as much as possible the same way across Living Labs, making comparisons across the Living Labs to some extent possible. This Monitoring Framework is described in the present report, including indicators needed to perform a quantitative and realist evaluation. Since the realist evaluation including quantitative and qualitative analysis needs context and mechanisms as well as outcomes to be described, the specific intervention package needs to be known. In addition, these contexts and mechanisms as well as (some) outcomes may change during the process. It is particularly for this realist evaluation that this monitoring framework report will be a 'living document', which needs updates as the project progresses.

This report is a starting point for monitoring the Synclusive project's data collection, but this process will evolve over time, according to the way the realist evaluation works, and will provide input for the tasks in WP2 and WP3. WP2 will involve designing and implementing the intervention package in each Living Lab. Work package 4 aims to monitor, assess and with this help may redirect the implementation process in WP2. The impact of implementing the intervention package in each Living Lab will be assessed in WP2. WP4 homogenises the datasets of the individual Living Labs for WP3. WP3 will compare the Living Labs and use multilevel perspective analyses to assess overall effects and describe the circumstances and prospects for upscaling. The monitoring framework and indicators identified will guide and support this both quantitative and qualitative process in both work packages.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE MONITORING FRAMEWORK

The monitoring framework (see figure 1) consists of several building blocks. It will use a mixed methods approach to data collection, encompassing the gathering, analysis, and interpretation of quantitative and qualitative data.

The first starting point for the framework is the **ENGINE outcomes**, which relate to the two main goals of this project: 1) to stimulate the inflow of vulnerable job seekers and 2) to stimulate upward and sideward mobility of vulnerable employees in the organisations in the region.

The second starting point is **the four living labs**, in which the ENGINE will be implemented. To be able to perform overall analyses across living labs (WP3), indicators that are measured in the same way in all four Living Labs need to be developed. We call those **generic core indicators**. In addition, for the ENGINE to work in those different countries, similar but also different interventions need to be implemented across countries. For the latter interventions, Living Lab specific outcome indicators are higher inflow and mobility, being the mid-term outcomes, for example, improved skills or better job coaching, increased employer support. These indicators may be highly specific for a specific Living Lab and reflect e.g., the specific skills to be developed by either the vulnerable job seekers, or the employees in the participating organisations related to the specific sector the organisation(s) belong to.

The final starting point is the **measurement level**. In this project, three main levels of intervention can be identified. Interventions will be directed at the **individual level** (i.e., job seekers and vulnerable employees), and changes in, for example, self-efficacy and skills of job seekers or vulnerable employees, are needed before employment or up/sideward mobility is possible. Interventions may also be directed at the **organisational level**, for example at the employer or management, to improve their attitude towards the inflow and up/sideward mobility of their employees within the organisation. Finally, we promote an active **regional coalition** of stakeholders, in which the municipality closely works together with employers in the region and other relevant stakeholders such as training institutions and civil society organisations (including regional social security organisations).

These three starting points translate into two goals for the framework: evaluation of the impact of the implementation packages in and across the four the Living Labs and understanding what works or not, for whom, in which circumstances, and why. For the first aim, a quantitative evaluation, and for the second aim realist evaluation needs to be performed, with underlying methodology and indicators (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Building blocks and outline of the monitoring framework.

In this project, we will study the impact of the intervention package on the core generic outcome indicators and on the Living Lab-specific outcome indicators. For the quantitative analyses we will assess the effectiveness of the intervention packages in the four Living Labs. This relation will be moderated they may relate either to the individual (e.g. the age of the person or the period of being unemployed), the organisation (e.g. its' size or inclusive policy) as well as the region (e.g. cultural aspects or the cohesion or goal-directedness of the collaboration between coalition partners). In the realist evaluation, we will also assess what mechanisms are at play and why specific interventions do or do not work for a specific person and/or in a specific situation. So along the process of realist evaluation, we may identify mechanisms that appear to have an important moderating impact on the impact of the intervention(package). These may be specific to one Living Lab but may also appear to tap into overarching mechanisms. During the implementation process, the realist evaluation may, therefore, identify relevant mechanisms which moderate the impact of the interventions and may thus have to be taken into account in the quantitative analyses.

For all analyses (quantitative and qualitative analysis), a set of various outcomes, as well as moderating indicators need to be identified or selected. Some general criteria will apply:

1. **Relevance:** The indicator(s) should be relevant to what it is intended to measure in this project, i.e., to the impact of the intervention packages of each Living Lab: (1) inflow of vulnerable unemployed into employment, facilitated by (2) upward or sideward mobility of employees in the participating organisations. It will be preferred to employ (registered) indicators, measured the same way in each Living Lab or questionnaires that have been validated in various languages, such as Finnish, Dutch, Portuguese, and Bulgarian, for the core generic outcome or moderator indicators. If questionnaires are not available in (one of) these four languages, they will be translated and retroactively translated.
2. **Reliability:** To measure the same indicator in a reliable way the indicators need to have a high consistency or test-retest reliability.

3. **Usability:** The number of indicators should be limited in number and be as short and concise as possible to limit the burden for participants. The usability will also be tested considering few participants.

Chapter 3 and 4 of the current report present the realist evaluation and multilevel analysis, respectively. In these chapters, we describe more specifically the indicators, and how they will be operationalised.

3. REALIST EVALUATION

The central question of realist evaluation is "What interventions work for which (specific) individuals, under which conditions, and why?" (Pawson et al., 2005). Realist evaluation acknowledges the existence of a real world, which we perceive and understand through our senses, cognitive processes, and cultural influences (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010). However, the interpretation of this reality is highly influenced by external factors (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010) such as social, and economic. This approach seeks to identify, test, and refine the components of interventions that are effective and those that are not (Pawson et al., 2005). Realist evaluation focuses on three core elements: context, mechanism, and outcome (Pawson et al., 2005). Essentially, interventions yield successful outcomes when they provide appropriate mechanisms or resources in suitable contexts. This relationship can be expressed as the formula "context + mechanism = outcome" (Pawson et al., 2005). Multiple context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configurations can be proposed and tested for an intervention, with the emphasis on understanding the relationships within each CMO (Pawson et al., 2005).

The realist evaluation approach follows the following four key steps:

1. Program theory: Identify the adequate theories to setting the CMO configurations (Johnson & Davis, 2019).
2. Hypotheses: Develop hypothetical CMO configurations that explore what might work for whom, under what circumstances, and why (Johnson & Davis, 2019).
3. Evidence-based: Test the theory by collecting data on the CMO configurations, utilising a mixed-methods approach that incorporates both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis (Johnson & Davis, 2019).
4. Analysis and synthesis: Identify what worked for whom, under what circumstances, and why (Johnson & Davis, 2019).

The application of this process to Synclusive project will work as follows:

3.1 Step 1: Program theory

Theories of change regarding unemployed vulnerable people focus on understanding the underlying mechanisms and pathways through which various factors interact and lead to better employment or mobility. In the case of our project, we will use middle range theories (table 1), as they are less abstract than grand theories but more general

than specific program theories. These theories help explain how different interventions produce outcomes in specific contexts. To meet the goals of the project the following middle range theories will be used.

Table 1 – First Approach to Middle Range Theories

<p>Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) (Bandura, 1997):</p>	<p>Self-Efficacy: SCCT emphasises self-efficacy as a critical factor in career transitions. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their capabilities to succeed in specific situations or tasks. In career transitions, higher self-efficacy leads to increased motivation, effort, and persistence in pursuing new career paths.</p> <p>Outcome Expectations: This theory also considers outcome expectations—individuals' beliefs about the outcomes of their actions—as influential in career decision-making and transition processes. (Bandura, 1997)</p>
<p>The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) of Change (Prochaska & Norcross, 2018):</p>	<p>Stages of Change: TTM posits that individuals go through different stages when making behavioural changes. These stages include pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, maintenance, and termination. During a career transition, individuals may traverse these stages as they contemplate, prepare for, and execute changes in their career.</p> <p>Self-Efficacy and Decisional Balance: Self-efficacy plays a crucial role in each stage, influencing an individual's belief in their ability to make the change and maintain it. Decisional balance refers to the weighing of pros and cons associated with change, impacting an individual's readiness to transition. (Prochaska & Norcross, 2018)</p>

<p>Career Construction Theory (Savickas, 2011):</p>	<p>Career Adaptability: This theory emphasises adaptability as crucial for career transitions. It comprises of four components—concern, control, curiosity, and confidence—that influence an individual’s capacity to handle career transitions effectively. (Savickas, 2011)</p> <p>Life Themes and Self-Concept: Career Construction Theory also considers how individuals construct their career narratives, drawing on personal experiences, values, and goals. This construction process influences career decisions and transitions.</p>
<p>Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991):</p>	<p>Behavioural Intentions: TPB suggests that behavioural change is influenced by an individual's intentions to perform a behaviour. In the context of career transitions, intentions to change careers are influenced by attitudes towards the transition, subjective norms (social influences), and perceived behavioural control (similar to self-efficacy). (Ajzen, 1991)</p> <p>Perceived Behavioural Control: Similar to self-efficacy, perceived behavioural control refers to the perceived ease or difficulty of performing a behaviour, such as transitioning to a new career.</p> <p>Cognitive-Behavioural Theory:</p> <p>Cognitive Restructuring: This theory focuses on how changing thoughts and beliefs can lead to changes in behaviour. During career transitions, individuals might need to reframe their beliefs about themselves, their abilities, and their career possibilities to successfully adapt to a new career path.</p>

	<p>Goal Setting and Action Planning: Cognitive-behavioural approaches often emphasise the importance of setting specific, achievable goals and creating action plans to facilitate behavioural change during career transitions. (Brown & Lent, 2016; Hirschi & Herrmann, 2012)</p>
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3.2 Step 2: CMO Configurations

The realist evaluation questions that emerged from the project application are the following:

1. What are the contexts (socio-political landscape, social security system, vulnerable people, organisations, and regional coalition) that influence mechanisms/interventions?
2. What are the mechanisms to increase the inflow of vulnerable groups into the labour market or sideways/upwards mobility?
3. What are the determinants (barriers and enablers) of delivering interventions to support vulnerable people to inflow into the labour market or move sideways/upwards in organisations?

Realist evaluation theories illustrate the relationship between contexts, mechanisms and outcomes configurations (context–mechanism–outcome). For each Living lab, we will describe the main potential interventions and configurations (table 2).

Interventions do not only impact the individuals directly involved; they can also lead to positive changes in participants' workplaces. Enhanced teamwork, productivity, and morale often result from improved skills and knowledge gained through these interventions (Smith & Johnson, 2020). Additionally, the positive outcomes extend beyond the workplace, with participants becoming more engaged in their communities and contributing positively to local economies and social structures.

Interventions designed for vulnerable unemployed individuals should be focused on or tailored to address the specific challenges they face. Realist evaluation can help understand how such interventions work, and it often uncovers a range of potential strategies. In table 2 there are some examples (not necessarily all applied in this

research project) of how specific interventions for vulnerable unemployed people might work, considering a realist evaluation perspective.

Table 2 – Examples of CTMO Configurations (for retrodution during the ENGINE implementation in each Living Lab)

Skills Training and Education Programs	Context: High unemployment rates, low educational attainment, and lack of marketable skills.
	Treatment: Skills training.
	Mechanism: Increasing confidence and improved skills.
	Outcome: Increased employability or mobility.
Job Coaching and Mentoring	Context: Limited work experience or barriers to employment due to personal circumstances.
	Treatment: Guidance and Support.
	Mechanism: Improving self-efficacy.
	Outcome: Improved job search skills, and employment and mobility.
Subsidised Employment Programs	Context: Limited access to job opportunities, especially for vulnerable groups.
	Treatment: Job coaching associated with pay subsidies to help to find more stable job.
	Mechanism: Less ‘stress’ due to reduced financial uncertainty
	Outcome: Increased employment rates, wage growth, and reduced reliance on social assistance.
Mental Health and Counseling Services	Context: Vulnerable individuals with mental health issues that affect their employability.
	Treatment: IPS (individual placement and support), CBT (Cognitive Behavioural Therapy) training and/or medication
	Mechanism: Emotional resilience.
	Outcome: Improved mental well-being, reduced absenteeism, and increased job retention.
Community-Based Employment Support	Context: Isolation and limited access to support networks.

	Treatment: Host networking events.
	Mechanism: creating a sense of belonging.
	Outcome: Improved social integration, increased employment stability.
Flexible Work Arrangements and Accommodations	Context: Physical disabilities or health conditions.
	Treatment: physical accessibility improvements 'automatic doors/ramps' 'user friendly computer assistance' job modifications
	Mechanism: Increased sense of belonging.
	Outcome: Improved job retention, reduced absenteeism.
Financial Literacy and Budgeting Workshops	Context: Financial instability and poverty.
	Treatment: Financial management skills training.
	Mechanism: Reduced economic stress.
	Outcome: Improved employment and mobility.
Social Enterprise Development	Context: Marginalised and disadvantaged communities.
	Treatment: Training and financial support for startup entrepreneurs
	Mechanism: Developing trust in the community.
	Outcome: Increased community development, employment opportunities, and skills acquisition.
Peer Support Groups	Context: Vulnerable individuals facing similar challenges.
	Treatment: Peer support forums.
	Mechanism: reduced feelings of isolation, peer learning, improved learning motivaton.
	Outcome: Improved self-esteem, better coping strategies.

Adapted Realistic evaluation (Pawson & Tilley, 1997)

The **Context** plays a pivotal role in shaping the conditions under which our intervention packages are introduced. It is crucial to understand the existing social and economic landscape, educational background, and employment opportunities for vulnerable

individuals. These contextual factors can significantly influence the success or failure of the efforts that will be made. Identifying the specific vulnerabilities is a fundamental step, as they can emerge from various sources, including disability, low income, lack of education, or social exclusion. Understanding the unique challenges faced by these groups helps to tailor our interventions effectively.

In realist evaluation, "context" refers to the conditions or circumstances in which an intervention or program is implemented. Identifying indicators for context involves understanding the factors that shape the context in which the intervention operates. These indicators (table 3) can help assess the contextual conditions that influence the outcomes and effectiveness of the intervention. Here are some indicators to consider when examining the context in the realist evaluation (Greenhalgh et al., 2007; Manzano, 2016; O'Cathain et al., 2019; Pawson & Tilley, 1997; Wong et al., 2016).

Table 3 – Context specific indicators (for retrodution during the ENGINE implementation in each Living Lab)

Socioeconomic Conditions:	Labour market regulations
Poverty levels	Anti-discrimination laws
Income disparities	Social welfare policies
Unemployment rates	Minimum wage laws
Access to education and healthcare	
	Local Labour Market Conditions:
Geographic Factors:	Availability of jobs
Urban or rural setting	Industry sectors
Proximity to employment opportunities	Job demand and supply
Availability of transportation	
	Educational and Training Facilities:
Demographic Characteristics:	Accessibility to educational institutions
Age distribution	Availability of vocational training
Gender composition	
Ethnic and cultural diversity	Technology and Digital Access:
Education	Access to the internet and digital tools
	Technological infrastructure
Policy and Legal regulations:	Digital literacy levels

The **Mechanisms** represent the core processes and resources that, when engaged within a given context, generate outcomes. Mechanisms encompass strategies for overcoming psychological barriers. Table 4 describes some mechanisms that might be relevant in our project. The mechanisms link the context with the outcomes.

Table 4 – Example of Mechanisms (for retrodution during the ENGINE implementation in each Living Lab)

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- a) Motivation is a common psychological mechanism that can be triggered by a program. When individuals are motivated, they are more likely to engage with the program and take action to achieve its goals. This can be especially important in health promotion programs, educational interventions, and behavioural change interventions.
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- b) Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their own ability to accomplish a specific task or goal. Interventions that enhance self-efficacy can empower individuals to act and make positive changes.
-
- c) Trust can motivate individuals to engage with and participate in an intervention, as they believe it will deliver the expected benefits and outcomes.
-
- d) Self-esteem is the subjective evaluation of one's self-worth. It involves the beliefs and feelings a person holds about their own competence, significance, and value as an individual.
-
- e) Stress is a response when an individual perceives a gap between the demands placed on them and their ability to cope with those demands.
-
- f) Fear is an emotional and physiological response to a real or perceived threat, danger, or harm.
-
- g) Beliefs and attitudes can shape behaviors and responses to interventions.
-

The **Outcomes** for vulnerable individuals resulting from interventions can encompass several dimensions as skill mastery, where participants acquire and demonstrate

proficiency in specific skills or more general career advancement skills relevant to their desired employment or career advancement. The newfound competences often lead to increased employability and better job prospects, providing individuals with access to more challenging opportunities in the job market (table 5). For reasons of efficiency and clarity we strive for the same outcomes in the realist evaluation as in the quantitative evaluation.

Table 5 – Main Outcomes

Main Outcomes
Inflow labour market
Up/sideward mobility

3.3 Step 3: Evidence-based on Mixed Method Approach

Mixed methods approach to data collection is used which encompasses the gathering, analysis, and interpretation of both quantitative and qualitative data, which is particularly advantageous for studying complex interactions (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). This method enables the triangulation of data from diverse sources, facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of the data and involving an iterative explanation-building process (Astbury & Leeuw, 2010).

3.4 Step 4: Analysis and Synthesis

The data collected will be coded and analysed. In addition to revealing potential interventions, this combined analysis will attempt to identify emerging trends in the relationships between contexts, mechanisms, and outcomes. The knowledge gathered from this data analysis will be used to improve and fine-tune the interventions.

4. MULTILEVEL ANALYSES

4.1 Defining the indicators - generic core outcome indicators and specific outcome indicators

To evaluate the impact of the intervention package, a quantitative evaluation will be performed. The quantitative approach allows monitoring generic core outcome indicators and Living Lab specific outcome indicators on individual, organisational and regional coalition level.

The indicators span multiple tiers, offering a comprehensive lens to gauge various facets concerning employment, and mobility within different levels of analysis - individual, organizational, regional coalition, and the living lab.

Within the organisational and regional coalition, the emphasis lies on engaging employers in these transitions and tasks, fostering collaboration among various stakeholders such as organizations, municipalities, regional social security entities, and training/coaching institutes.

At individual and at the living lab levels examines into the specifics of targeted job seekers or employees in mobility, meticulously detailing interventions implemented to enhance employability - including their scope, and duration. It further examines the impact by monitoring the number of individuals gaining employment due to these interventions and the duration they stay employed, differentiating between various types of contracts. Additionally, it scrutinizes the mobility of vulnerable employees in companies via the Living Lab intervention and contrasts it with those gaining mobility to more challenging jobs without this intervention, employing instruments like Living Lab registrations, interviews, or logbooks for data collection.

4.2 Mediators and Moderators

The mediation role of a variable refers to the process through which the variable transmits or carries the effect of an independent variable to a dependent variable. In the case of the ENGINE, the mediation roles of employability, mobility, self-efficacy, confidence, and trust are crucial factors to influence the outcomes including inflow in the labour market and upward or sideward mobility in organisations.

Employability stands as a significant mediating factor between education and employment outcomes. It embodies an individual's skills, knowledge, and abilities to secure and maintain employment (Johnson & Davis, 2019). Research often showcases how education influences employability, subsequently affecting job attainment and career success (Savickas, 2011). For instance, education attainment tends to correlate with better employability prospects, acting as a mediator between education and job outcomes.

Mobility, in terms of organisational movement, may act as a mediator of the relationship between job opportunities and performance rates. An organisation offering more internal job opportunities might have more mobility of employees as individuals move to access these opportunities, subsequently impacting performance rates.

Self-efficacy, confidence, and trust may serve as mediators in personal development and decision-making processes. Self-efficacy, rooted in one's belief in their ability to accomplish tasks, may mediate the relationship between goal setting and performance outcomes. Confidence may mediate the link between self-perception and actions taken towards personal or professional goals. Trust may be a mediator between interpersonal relationships, influencing collaboration, and cooperation in various settings.

Understanding these mediating effects has substantial implications. For instance, interventions aimed at enhancing employability skills among young people may indirectly influence their career trajectories. Similarly, initiatives fostering mobility might have broader implications for regional employment patterns. Enhancing self-efficacy, confidence, and trust may positively impact individual decision-making and interpersonal relationships, ultimately affecting personal and professional success. Through regression-based models or structural equation modelling, it is possible to assess the direct and indirect effects of variables if we can reach an adequate sample size.

Also, the moderator variables can influence the strength or direction of a relationship between two other variables. These variables can help identify conditions under which a particular independent variable has a stronger or weaker effect on a dependent variable. Here are some examples of moderator variables:

- Gender: The relationship between levels of qualification and employment may be moderated by gender, with the effect being stronger for one gender than the other.
- Age: The impact of a new training methodologies may be moderated by age, with younger students benefiting more than older students.

- Motivation: the relationship between more challenging tasks may be moderated by individual motivation levels, with highly motivated employees responding more positively.

In the examples of mediators and moderators mainly individual level variables are identified. However, these types of variables may also be active at the organisational, regional or national level. For example, company size might be acting as a moderator at the organisational level. While it has been suggested that smaller firms are more flexible and able to adapt to market trends, they are also described as isolated and lacking the necessary 'slack' resource capacity for engaging in activities such as skills development. In addition, companies who already adopted an 'inclusive labour market policy' may also be more prone to work on personnel skills and put an effort in the enrolment of vulnerable workers. Furthermore, in this project it is assumed that regional collaboration of different stakeholders might lead to more inclusion of vulnerable people in employment as well as more skill development and mobility of employees. Particularly in case this has been the goal of the coalition. If investigating moderators will not be possible because of the restriction on the number of coalitions, then only will be done a simpler quantitative analysis.

In addition, legislation and subsidies, but also cultural values may result in more companies adopting such inclusive policies. The identification and understanding of mediators and moderator variables can enhance the precision of research findings and defining interventions for vulnerable unemployed people.

4.3 Planning of the measurement points

During the start and implementation of the intervention package in each living lab, there will be three measuring moments (in each measurement level: at the level of the individual this means a repeated measures (if possible) within each participant). At the individual level a within-person follow-up measurement (before, during and after the intervention) will be performed.

At the organisational and regional coalition level, measurements will also be performed at three times (or maybe even more, dependent on the intervention package) during the implementation of the intervention package, aiming for monitoring the impact of the

intervention package. If possible, timing measurements across Living Labs will be harmonised. However, the effective implementation of the intervention package will inform about the best moments for the data collection.

The aim for the repeated measurement will be to analyse the impact of the intervention on those three levels. At each level, it will be important to check which indicators are expected to be sensitive to the implementation of (this part of) the intervention package: T0 - before the interventions; T1 - during the interventions; T2 - after the interventions (Figure 2). However, specific dates and time intervals between the measurements will depend on the type of interventions or intervention package planned and implemented. The planning can thus be made more specific when the action plans for the Living Labs have been completed (Task 1.4).

Figure 2 - Timeline for Data Collection for individual Core Indicators (Quantitative).

4.4 Methods to determine the number of participants in the Living Labs

To show a significant impact of the intervention package per Living Lab or across Living Labs, a specific number of vulnerable employees will be needed who may or may not become mobile (up or sideways) and of vulnerable job seekers who do or do not flow into the labour market, but characteristics of the regional labour market may, for example, affect these numbers.

A power analysis (Myors and Murphy, 2023) will be essential for determining the minimum sample size required to adequately test an effect at the appropriate level of significance within each Living Lab.

However, an ad hoc rule can be also applied: considering ten (10) observations per independent variable at a minimum, this means that only can be include 3 - 4 independent variables in each Living Lab. With these conditions in mind, the entire sample including the distinction between enrolled and not enrolled at the multi-level (i.e. in all countries) a number of minimally 72 participants per Living Lab would be needed. In addition, the recruitment rate or non-response to enrolment may differ per vulnerable group. This would mean that the source population which has to be contacted for enrolment amongst job seekers as well as amongst employees should at least be 720 vulnerable job seekers and (low-skilled) employees during the implementation period (i.e. 32 months (WP2)). For (unemployed) young people (in Portugal) the enrolment rate is expected to be higher. As for the older women (55+, Bulgaria) or long-term unemployed in Finland there are no information or estimation on the enrolment.

With these numbers, depending on the assumptions made, discussions with partners in the field (e.g. municipalities) indicate that it is unlikely that enough employees and vulnerable job seekers will be enrolled within the 32 months of the WP2 duration. This is for a large part due to the unexpected tight labour market and the relatively low number of vulnerable job seekers in a region. As an alternative, we try to use reference data for the questionnaires at the national or regional level and give a perspective on what happened during the implementation period in WP2 with the groups that enrolled in the intervention program of the Living Lab. Or reference data may be collected from employees from a different team or department, or from a group of unemployed job seekers who for one reason or another did not enter/enrol into the intervention package.

4.5 Multilevel Perspective Analysis

Conducting a multilevel perspective analysis of data related to interventions for unemployed people and employees in mobility will be a goal and the focus will be on understanding how individual characteristics and the Living Lab environment (group-level) interact to influence employment outcomes. The multilevel analysis allows (when possible) to examine how the impact of interventions may vary at different levels (individual and living lab) and how these levels influence each other. The multi-level perspective will be from the 'lens' of the vulnerable individuals based on interviews and

secondary data reflections from organisations and regional entities, dependent on the sample size.

Multilevel analysis will involve statistical analysis, such as robust cluster analysis and/or multi-level mixed estimation, to analyse data from unemployed individuals with interventions in Living Labs using comparison group, and experiment design. These techniques are used to examine the relationships between individual-level and Living Lab-level variables and how they jointly influence the outcomes.

5. INSTRUMENTS AND INDICATORS FOR REALIST EVALUATION AND MULTILEVEL ANALYSIS

Since it is intended to standardise the core generic outcome indicators to measure them the same way across Living Labs, a suggestion is done in table 6 below for the identification of these indicators.

Table 6 – Indicators to be measured in each Living Lab and Instruments

Indicator level	Target	indicator
Individual	Employee(s) of organisations in the coalition who want to develop talents/are aimed to be mobilised Job seeker: Unemployed long duration (>=1 year) – 1 st job; new job Women + 55 Others not searching formally for job	Questionnaire Profile and skills Inventory to measure general skills (annex 1) Self-efficacy scale (annex 2) Job seeking activity scale (annex 3) Expectation Organisational Mobility Scale (annex 4; 5) Interventions Evaluation (Coacher/Trainer; Job Seeker/Employee) (annex 6; 7) Instrument: 'Questionnaires

<p>Organisation</p>	<p>Employers (within organisations)</p>	<p>How many transitions towards other/more challenging positions (during last 1 year).</p> <p>And/or</p> <p>How many new or more challenging tasks have been taken by employees (during last (1) year).</p> <p>Instrument: Logbook, registration, or Interview (annex 9)</p> <p>Internal mobility rate = (total number of internal movements/total number of employees) x 100</p>
<p>Regional coalition</p>	<p>Organisation, municipality or regional social security, organisation/training or coaching institute</p> <p>Training institutes</p>	<p>Partnerships Analysis Tool (Annex 8)</p> <p>Instrument: Questionnaires</p>
<p>Living Lab</p>		<p>Indicators:</p> <p>(1) how many job seekers (or inactive persons) were targeted</p> <p>(2) which interventions/measures (how many, how long, how much cost) were taken to increase their employability</p> <p>(3) how many entered employment</p> <p>(4) how many stayed in the employment (to be considered all the situations: 1 month, half a year, fixed term, or permanent contract).</p>

		<p>(5) new vulnerable employees entered the company through the Living Lab intervention.</p> <p>(6) number of vulnerable employees who entered the company without the Living lab intervention.</p> <p>Instrument: LL registrations, interviews, or logbooks.</p>
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All four Living labs will analyse change in the outcome indicators (both generic and specific), based on data collected with the questionnaire(s) and the collection of registered information and/or interviews, allowing to understand the results of the four Living Labs.

6. PLANNING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE LIVING LABS

The goal is to make the process of realist evaluation iterative, and continuously assess and refine interventions based on ongoing feedback, data collection, and analysis, to create a culture of learning and adaptation within the living labs.

In the next table (7) it is showed a representation of the roles and responsibilities during the next 2 years of the project, for the implementation of the Living Labs, and the process of monitoring the interventions and the outcomes of the ENGINE.

Year 2024/ 2025	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
Months 3-24: Interventions																								
Trainers: Implement the action plans for interventions within each living lab (WP1).																								
Municipalities, communities: Provide necessary support and resources for the implementation of the intervention's programs.																								
Months 3-24: Data Collection																								
Researchers: Lead data collection efforts using mixed methods (questionnaires, interviews,).																								
Trainers: Implement participatory approaches, e.g., mentoring, and coaching processes for empowerment and insights gathering.																								
Months 7-9: Analyze and Refine Program Theories																								
Researchers: Analyse collected data to refine and validate program theories.																								

Year 2024/ 2025	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
Months 8-10: Test and Iterate Interventions																								
Researchers, Trainers: Based on analysis, adjust interventions within the living labs.																								
Regional Organizations: Provide support and resources for modifying programs or structures.																								
Months 4-21: Document and Disseminate Findings																								
Researchers: Create comprehensive reports outlining the realist evaluation process and key findings.																								
Regional Organizations: Assist in disseminating information to stakeholders, policymakers, other living labs, and academia.																								
Months 22-24: Evaluation and Future Planning																								
Researchers: Evaluate the effectiveness of the realist evaluation process.																								

Year 2024/ 2025	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
All stakeholders: Collaborate to plan potential follow-up studies or interventions based on identified gaps or new insights.																								

GLOSSARY: THE MAIN CONCEPTS

Causal Inference: pertains to understanding the cause-and-effect relationships between programs and outcomes in specific contexts. Both qualitative and quantitative data are used to make causal claims (Manzano, 2016; Wong et al., 2013). For example, in a realist evaluation of a job training program for the unemployed, researchers may use both quantitative and qualitative data to make causal inferences. By comparing the survey data on program participation and job placement rates (quantitative) with the narratives from interviews with program participants (qualitative), researchers can draw conclusions about the causal relationships between interventions as acquisition of skills from training unlocks a mechanism such as self-efficacy (mechanism) and employment outcomes (outcome) within the context of the local job market (context). Causal inference allows for a comprehensive understanding of the program's impact.

Context-Mechanism-Outcome (CMO) Configuration: are the core components of realist evaluation. They describe the relationship between the contextual factors (C), the mechanisms (M), and the outcomes (O) of an intervention. Understanding these configurations is essential for explaining how and why the programs work. An example of a CMO configuration might be how the presence of a strong community support might impact social inclusion of vulnerable people.

Context-Mechanism-outcome (CMO) Configurations Testing: is the process of testing and refining the CMO configurations through empirical data collection, usually involving surveys, interviews, observations, and analysis to validate or revise the theoretical explanations. In a realist evaluation of a school bullying prevention program, CMO configurations may be tested by conducting interviews with students, teachers, and parents to understand how the mechanisms of peer support and teacher intervention interact with contextual factors like school policies, ultimately affecting bullying outcomes.

Context: is the specific circumstances, settings, and conditions in which a social program or intervention is implemented, including the cultural, organizational, and environmental factors that influence its operation. For instance, when assessing a job training program's effectiveness, the context may include factors like local economic conditions, the availability of job opportunities, and the educational background of participants (Marchal et al., 2012).

Employability: concept established by Feintuch in 1955, has been recognized as a crucial factor for attaining future paid employment. In the period leading up to the 1980s, research on employability predominantly centred around examining the employability of individuals facing unemployment and vulnerable groups within the labour market, as noted by Forrier et al. in 2015.

Intervention: the program, policy, or action that is being evaluated.

Mechanism: are the underlying processes, responses, or interactions that generate outcomes in a specific context. They are the "black-box" explanations for why interventions work or do not work (Dalkin et al., 2015).

Middle-Range Theories: are more general than program-specific theories but less abstract than grand theories, are frequently used in realist evaluation. These theories aid in the explanation of how certain interventions result in particular outcomes in given circumstances (Porter et al., 2019).

Mixed Methods: combines both qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis techniques. This approach offers a comprehensive understanding of program mechanisms and outcomes. In evaluating the integration of refugees into the labour market, mixed methods may involve using qualitative interviews to explore how cultural sensitivity training (intervention) influences successful job placement (outcome), while also quantitatively measuring employment rates among the refugee population (Manzano, 2016; Wong et al., 2013).

Organisational Mobility: refers to employees' internal mobility within organizations. This focus is driven by the need for adaptable workforces that can readily undertake diverse tasks, enabling companies to evolving business landscapes while retaining skilled personnel (Cappelli, 1999). Employers need to align their mobility opportunities with employees' expectations and abilities (Schein, 1978).

Outcome: in the scope of this project, it refers to inflow and mobility. For instance, in an employment training program, different patterns of outcomes may emerge among participants with varying levels of prior work experience, demonstrating the role of mechanisms like self-efficacy in job placement success (Manzano, 2016).

Process Evaluation: is a qualitative method used in realist evaluation to assess the implementation of a program or intervention, focusing on how it was carried out, the interactions between stakeholders, and any unexpected changes that occurred during the intervention. For example, in assessing a program for the employment of ex-convicts, process evaluation may involve interviewing program coordinators to understand how contextual factors, such as community support and employer engagement, influenced the program's implementation (Manzano, 2016; Dalkin et al., 2015).

Program Theory: is a model or framework that outlines the underlying assumptions about how an intervention is expected to work, including the mechanisms that should be triggered and the outcomes that should result. For example, in a youth mentoring program, the program theory may hypothesize that the mechanism of positive role modeling will lead to improved self-esteem and future educational attainment as outcomes (Greenhalgh et al., 2017).

Qualitative Data: includes non-numerical information such as interview transcripts, observations, and written or visual materials. It is used to explore context, mechanisms, and outcomes in-depth, providing rich descriptions and insights. For example, in a realist evaluation of a job training program for unemployed individuals, qualitative data might include interview transcripts with program participants to understand the context, mechanisms, and outcomes of their integration into the labour market (Manzano, 2016; Dalkin et al., 2015).

Quantitative Data: consists of numerical information, often collected through surveys, tests, or structured assessments. It helps in measuring and comparing the presence or absence of outcomes and the extent to which mechanisms are triggered. For instance, in a study on the employment of individuals with disabilities, quantitative data might reveal the percentage of participants who secured long-term employment (outcome) and the relationship between their participation in skills training programs (mechanism) and their employment status (Wong et al., 2013; Marchal et al., 2012).

Realist Evaluation: is an evaluation framework that aims to uncover the underlying mechanisms that explain how and why social programs or interventions produce their outcomes in specific contexts (Pawson & Tilley, 1997).

Retroduction: is a process to develop and refine CMO configurations. Retroduction involves making educated guesses or hypotheses about the mechanisms underlying program outcomes and then testing these hypotheses through empirical data collection. This process relies on deductive reasoning, drawing on existing theories and knowledge about human behaviour.

Skilling and Reskilling: concepts play pivotal roles in shaping individuals' career trajectories. Skilling, at its core, is about equipping oneself with the skills necessary for a current job or career (Smith & Johnson, 2020). This involves the acquisition of competencies that are directly relevant to one's existing role, ensuring that they can perform their tasks efficiently and stay competitive in their profession.

Theory Testing: involves evaluating whether the hypothesized program theory and CMO configurations are supported by the collected qualitative and quantitative data. It aims to refine and validate the theory based on empirical evidence. In a study on the reintegration of formerly incarcerated individuals, theory testing may involve assessing whether the interventions, such as skills acquisition through vocational training, align with the actual employment outcomes of program participants (Wong et al., 2013; Pommier et al., 2015).

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Annex List

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Annex 1 – Context Specific Indicators

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Questionnaire Profile and Skills Inventory

(Job Seekers and Employees)

To be applied T0; T1; T2

Reference number

Today's date (dd-mm-yy)

Moment of application (T0; T1; T2)

1. Personal details

1.1 Are you:

Male

Female

Other

1.2 Current age years

1.3 Level of qualifications:

Level 1: Basic Skills	
Level 2: Lower Secondary Education	
Level 3: Upper Secondary Education	
Level 4: Post Secondary Non-Tertiary Education	
Level 5: Short Cycle Education Tertiary	
Level 6: Bachelor's Degree or Equivalent	
Level 7: Master's Degree or Equivalent	
Level 8: Doctorate or Equivalent	

2. Which of the following best describes your current work situation? You may choose more than one option.

- a) Trainee
- b) Workshop work or rehabilitative work
- c) Work trial
- d) Unemployed (jobseeker at employment office)
- e) Unemployed (not a jobseeker at employment office)
- f) Non-paid work, for example voluntary or charity work
- g) Community service
- h) Student or apprentice
- i) At home (stay-at-home parent or carer)
- j) On sick leave or partial sick leave
- k) Retired
- l) Paid employee (full-time, part-time, work with pay subsidy)
- m) Self-employed or freelancer
- n) Work supported by a grant or scholarship

3. How long has your current period of unemployment lasted?

Less than a year

1–2 years

3–4 years

5–7 years

8–10 years

Over 10 years

I have never worked

I am not currently unemployed

4. How do you feel in relation to work life at the moment? Choose the number that best matches your situation.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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0 =	1–3 =	4–5 =	6–8 =	9–10 =
Work life or employment does not currently apply to me	I don't have a job. I'm poorly equipped for work life. I need support in order to obtain employment.	I don't have a job, but I am equipped for work life. I may need support in order to obtain employment.	I have a job. I am equipped for work life. I may however need support in order to stay in employment.	I have a job. I am well-equipped to continue in employment.

5. How difficult do the following situations make it for you to participate in work life?

	Extremely difficult	Rather difficult	Somewhat difficult	Slightly difficult	Not difficult at all	I don't know
	1	2	3	4	5	6
(13) Lack of job opportunities						
(14) Commuting difficulties for example: difficult transport connections, long distances.						
(15) Lack of training and skills for example: language skills, lack of professional qualifications or outdated qualifications						
(16) Diminished work motivation or desire to work						
(17) Problems connected to health or functional capacity						
(18) Personal life situation for example: family, relatives, friends						
(19) Substance dependence and other addictions						
(110) Criminal or drugs record						
(111) Financial situation For example: debts, enforcement orders						

Adapted from Abilitator, 2023

6. Assess your level of skills development:

To be applied T0; T1; T2

General Skill/Level of development	1 = none	2 = Beginner	3 = Intermediate	4 = Advanced
Capacity to learn				
Capacity for applying knowledge in practice				
Basic knowledge in a specific profession				
Teamwork				
Maintaining financial records				
Ability to work independently				
Problem solving				
Capacity to adapt to new situations				
Adaptability				
Capacity for analysis and synthesis				
Oral and written communication in your native language				
Information management skills (ability to retrieve and analyse information from different sources)				
Computing skills				
Capacity for generating new ideas (creativity)				
Decision-making				
Critical thinking				

Research skills				
Leadership				
Social skills				

Hard Skills/Level of development	1 = none	2 = Beginner	3 = Intermediate	4 = Advanced	Specify which skills
Technical skills (Specialist knowledge needed to perform job duties)					
Foreign language skills					
Customer handling skills (e.g. Selling a product/service; Dealing with people; Counselling, advising or caring for customers or clients)					
Planning and organisation skills (e.g. Planning the activities; Organising own or other's work time)					
Marketing Skills (Digital platforms, market research, e-commerce, content management)					
Tourism skills (travel agency, tourist guide, chef, tourism technician)					
Proximity services skills (Household, Caregivers, Hairdresser)					
Other:					

Annex 2 – Self-Efficacy scale

Self-efficacy Job Seekers and Employees

To be applied T0; T1; T2

Reference number	
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As an Employee and a Job Seeker assess your self-efficacy, responding to the following questionnaire, ranking the degree to which you agree in each statement, where 1 means “Strongly Disagree”, and 6 means “Strongly Agree”.

	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 disagree a little	4 agree a little	5 agree	6 strongly agree
1 I am able to cope with setbacks						
2 I am able to complete my work tasks						
3 I am able to set my personal boundaries at work						
4 I am able to perform my tasks at work						
5 I am able to deal with emotionally demanding situations						
6 I have energy left to do anything else						

7 I can concentrate on my work						
8 I can cope with work pressure						
9 I am able to handle potential problems at work						
10 I can motivate myself to perform my job						
11 I can deal with the physical demands of my work						

Annex 3 – Job-seeking activity scale

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Job-seekers

To be applied T0; T1; T2

Reference number

As a Job Seeker assess your willing to search for a job, responding to the following questionnaire:

1. Have you been searching for a job during the past month?	(yes/no)
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Those who answered `Yes' were further asked:

2. Items (1)-(5) were rated on a four-point scale:	1 = not at all	2 = once or twice during the month	3 = weekly	4 = daily.
(1) Have you been looking for vacancies at the local employment office?				
(2) Have you been following newspaper ads of vacancies?				
(3) Have you contacted employers without `official' advertisement of vacancies?				
(4) Have you been asking friends and neighbours for job opportunities?				
(5) Have you been looking for vacancies in industries that differ from your previous profession?				

In item (6), numbers of applications exceeding five were scored as 5.

(6) How many vacancies have you applied for during the past month?	
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The internal consistency coefficient of the six-item sum scale [sum of items (1)-(6)] was 0.69 at T1 (Cronbach's alpha).

Vesalainen, J., & Vuori, J. (1999). Job-seeking, adaptation and re-employment experiences of the unemployed: a three-year follow-up. *Journal of Community & Applied Social Psychology*, 9, 383-394.

Annex 4 – Employees Expected External Organizational Mobility

Funded by the
European Union

Employees Expected External Organizational Mobility

To be applied T0

Reference number

As an employee assess your organisational mobility expectations, responding to the following questionnaire:

1.	It is common in my profession to be actively searching for a job.	0 = No 1 = Yes
2.	It seems like many of my co-workers are looking for other jobs.	0 = No 1 = Yes
3.	I am actively looking for another job.	0 = No 1 = Yes
4.	In my profession, the best way to raise your salary is to change companies frequently.	0 = No 1 = Yes
5.	I have considered leaving to start my own company or to go into independent consulting.	0 = No 1 = Yes

Pearce, J. L., & Randel, A. E. (2004). Expectations of organizational mobility, workplace social inclusion, and employee job performance. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(1), 81–98. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.232>

Annex 5 – Employees Internal Organizational Mobility

Employees Internal Organizational Mobility

Reference number

To be applied TO

Please rank the degree to which you agree in each statement, where 1 means “Strongly Disagree”, and 6 means “Strongly Agree”

	1 'strongly disagree'	2 'disagree'	3 'disagree a little'	4 'agree a little'	5 'agree'	6 'strongly agree'.
IM1 The company provides me with real opportunities for promotions.						
IM2 The company allows me to ask for advancements.						
IM3 I have the training support I need from my organization.						
IM4 I have been looking new work opportunities in my current organization.						
IM5 I have applied more permanent position in my current organization						

Annex 6 – Interventions Evaluation Coahers/Trainers Questionnaire

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QUESTIONNAIRE

Trainers / Coachers

To be applied T2

Reference number

Trainer is asked to rate the impact of the interventions in the living labs to increase the employability and competencies of the vulnerable people on each item using a Likert scale from 1 to 6, where 1 indicates "Strongly Disagree" and 5 indicates "Strongly Agree".

	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 disagree a little	4 agree a little	5 agree	6 strongly agree
The training content was highly relevant to the specific needs of vulnerable participants.						
It was easy to communicate effectively and adapt the approach to connect with and						

support vulnerable participants.						
A high level of empathy and sensitivity toward the unique circumstances of vulnerable participants was easy to achieve.						
The training environment and materials were designed to be inclusive and accessible to all participants.						
Vulnerable participants were not engaged or motivated during the training.						
The training significantly improved the employability of vulnerable participants, increasing their chances of entering the labour market.						

Annex 7 – Interventions Evaluation Job Seekers and Employees Questionnaire

QUESTIONNAIRE

Job Seekers and Employees

To be applied T2

Reference number

Job Seekers and Employees are asked to rate the impact of the interventions in the living labs to increase their employability and competencies on each item using a Likert scale from 1 to 6, where 1 indicates "Strongly Disagree" and 5 indicates "Strongly Agree".

	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 disagree a little	4 agree a little	5 agree	6 strongly agree
The intervention / training content was highly relevant to my specific needs.						
The communication of the coacher/trainer was easy to understand.						
A high level of empathy and						

sensitivity was easy to achieve during the intervention.						
The intervention / training environment and materials were inclusive and accessible to me.						
I was not engaged or motivated during the intervention / training.						
The intervention/ training significantly increased the chances of entering the labour market.						

Annex 8 – Regional coalition

QUESTIONNAIRE REGIONAL COALITION

To be applied T1; T2

Reference number	
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Indicate the Living Lab: _____

To assess the regional coalition, respond to the following questionnaire.

Rate your level of agreement with each of the statements below, with 1 indicating strong disagreement and 5 indicating strong agreement. To subtotal your score for each section, add up the ranking for each question (for example: 2+3+1+5+2=13).

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Not sure	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
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1. Determining the need for the partnership

a) There is a perceived need for the partnership in terms of areas of common interest and complementary capacity.					
b) There is a clear goal for the partnership.					
c) There is a shared understanding of, and commitment to, this goal among all potential partners.					

d) The partners are willing to share some of their ideas, resources, influence and power to fulfil the goal.					
e) The perceived benefits of the partnership outweigh the perceived costs.					

2. Choosing partners

a) The partners share common ideologies, interests and approaches					
b) The partners see their core business as partially interdependent.					
c) There is a history of good relations between the partners.					
d) The partnership brings added prestige to the partners individually as well as collectively.					
e) There is enough variety among members to have a comprehensive understanding of the issues being addressed.					

3. Making sure partnerships work

a) The managers in each organisation (or division) support the partnership. Partners have the necessary skills for collaborative action.					
b) There are strategies to enhance the skills of the partnership through increasing the membership or workforce development.					

c) The roles, responsibilities and expectations of partners are clearly defined and understood by all other partners.					
d) The administrative, communication and decision-making structure of the partnership is as simple as possible.					

4. Planning collaborative action

a) All partners are involved in planning and setting priorities for collaborative action.					
b) Partners have the task of communicating and promoting the partnership in their own organisations.					
c) Some staff have roles that cross the traditional boundaries that exist between agencies or divisions in the partnership.					
d) The lines of communication, roles and expectations of partners are clear.					
e) There is a participatory decision-making system that is accountable, responsive and inclusive.					

5. Implementing collaborative action

a) Processes that are common across agencies have been standardised (e.g. referral protocols, service standards, data					
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collection and reporting mechanisms).					
b) There is an investment in the partnership of time, personnel, materials or facilities.					
c) Collaborative action by staff and reciprocity between agencies is rewarded by management.					
d) The action is adding value (rather than duplicating services) for the community, clients or agencies involved in the partnership.					
e) There are regular opportunities for informal and voluntary contact between staff from the different agencies and other members of the partnership.					

6. Minimising the barriers to partnerships

a) Differences in organisational priorities, goals and tasks have been addressed.					
b) There is a core group of skilled and committed (in terms of the partnership) staff that has continued over the life of the partnership.					
c) There are formal structures for sharing information and resolving demarcation disputes.					

d) There are informal ways of achieving this.					
e) There are strategies to ensure alternative views are expressed within the partnership.					

7. Reflecting on and continuing the partnership

a) There are processes for recognising and celebrating collective achievements and/or individual contributions.					
b) The partnership can demonstrate or document the outcomes of its collective work. There is a clear need for and commitment to continuing the collaboration in the medium term.					
c) There are resources available from either internal or external sources to continue the partnership.					
d) There is a way of reviewing the range of partners and bringing in new members or removing some.					

Aggregate score	
1. Determining the need for the partnership	
2. Choosing partners	
3. Making sure partnerships work	
4. Planning collaborative action	
5. Implementing collaborative action	

6. Minimising the barriers to partnerships	
7. Reflecting on and continuing the partnership	
TOTAL	

Checklists score

35–84 The whole idea of a partnership should be rigorously questioned.

85–126 The partnership is moving in the right direction, but it will need more attention if it is going to be successful.

127–175 A partnership based on genuine collaboration has been established. The challenge is to maintain its impetus and build on the current success.

Adapted from Cummings TG & Worley CG, 2004, *Organization Development & Change*, 8th edition, South-Western College Publishing, Mason, Ohio and McNamara C, 2005, *Field guide to consulting and organizational development*, Authenticity Consulting, LLC. To obtain the latter book, select 'Publications' at www.authenticityconsulting.com

Funded by the
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INTERVIEW GUIDE

Employers and managers

To be applied T0

Reference number

The aim of the interviews is to gather information about:

- Efforts of actors on eliminating discrimination
- Improving an inclusive work environment
- Inflow, promotion.

The information arisen from these focus groups will be triangulated with the review of literature, to highlight potential recommendations for organisations, stakeholders and for policy.

Topic 1: Background

1. What kind of task you are performing (or what kind of role you have) in this organisation?

2. What kind of experiences you have about the employment of the vulnerable group in concern?

Topic 2: Discrimination

3. What kind of efforts do you apply for eliminating discrimination?

Topic 3: Inclusivity

4. How do you promote an inclusive work environment? Do you feel that everyone is treated equally in the workplace, regardless of race, sex, religion, language, disability, or others?

Topic 3: Inflow job seekers

5. What kind of mechanisms do you use/suggest to inflow job seekers?

Topic 4: Mobility of employees

6. What kind of mechanisms do you use/suggest promoting employees? And how?